

Lab-scaled experiments investigating the energy capture potential in low-energy density flows

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This study investigates the hydrodynamic effects of integrating a novel lightweight stream tube capture device in-line with a hydrokinetic turbine for the purpose of increasing the power density. The goal of this novel technology is to enable rapidly deployable remote power generation in marine environments with low hydrokinetic potential. The objective of this study is to provide an empirical basis for quantitatively assessing feasibility and scaling. Component level laboratory experiments are being conducted in the large hydraulic flume facility (32ft long by 4ft wide by 15in depth) at low Froude and Reynolds number in the Fluid Mechanics Laboratory at Bucknell University. Analytical models are being developed to analyze the results and quantify the potential impact. Simplified potential flow simulations are used to help identify sensitivities to critical design variables.

Many marine environments exhibit low current velocities yielding low hydrokinetic energy density. A range of applications identified as critical for the future blue economy (ROVs, AUVs, Radar, Lidar, etc....) require power generation in the range 100's of W to 1's of kW. Locations relevant for these applications are likely to have low energy density and high costs associated with deployment and maintenance, which drive up the levelized cost of energy (LCOE). The proposed technology aims for an approximate order of magnitude improvement in power/weight ratio compared with traditional hydrokinetic turbine systems to be economically viable. The technology relies on the strategy of sacrificing a small amount of hydrodynamic efficiency for a large weight reduction.

Velocity and drag measurement are the primary metrics to determine the energy potential of the flow and momentum flux across the devices. A laser doppler velocimeter is used to determine the velocity and a custom drag sled containing a load cell has been constructed to determine the drag induced by the flow. Drag results indicate the pressure change induced by the device and two-dimensional velocity readings will be used to determine the mass and momentum flux through the system. A perforated plate is used to model the marine hydrokinetic turbine due to scaling limitations. The design of the plate has been guided by literature to match turbine dynamics at increased scale.